

Towards Sustainable Urban and Peri-Urban Areas: Evaluating the Role of Land Planning Laws in Tanzania

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Abstract:

Land planning laws are tools for achieving sustainable urban and peri-urban areas internationally, regionally, and nationally. This article evaluates the role of land planning laws in achieving sustainable urban and peri-urban areas in Tanzania. The article adopts the doctrinal legal research methodology to assess different land planning laws in Tanzania and their mechanisms to ensure sustainability in urban and peri-urban areas. Land planning laws significantly contribute to orderly and sustainable urban and peri-urban areas via planning consent, zoning restrictions, environmental impact assessment, urban planning space standards, designation of conservation areas, land suitability assessment, historical or architectural interests, and land use plans. However, the effectiveness of the land planning laws is limited because of the discretionary powers of land use, planning and management vested in the authorities responsible for enforcement. Therefore, this article calls for legislative amendments to enhance the enforcement of land planning laws to achieve sustainable urban and peri-urban areas in Tanzania.

Keywords: Land Planning Laws, Sustainable, Urban and Peri-Urban Areas, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Human activities in urban and peri-urban areas pose significant threats.¹ These areas experience rapid changes in land use. As a result, environmental degradation, loss of biodiversity, and socioeconomic challenges threaten livelihood in urban and peri-urban areas. Rapid population growth and reclassification of rural areas to urban status are the main drivers of rapid urbanisation, which eventually poses risks. In their study, Mnyali and Materu analysed the current and future land use/land cover changes in peri-urban areas of Dar es Salaam City in 2021.² The results of their study show that 33.7% of vegetation has been lost due to increased settlements over the past two decades.

Linear development patterns of built-up areas in this study have gained about 30% of other land covers. Henceforth, this study predicts a drastic increase of built-up areas that occupy 51.6% by 2039 and, on the other hand, a decrease of vegetation and water cover that occupy 40.4% and 1.4%, respectively. Corroboratively, Munuo and Matindana investigated modelling expansion and densification in peri-urban areas.³ Their case study was Goba Ward in Dar Es Salaam. This study found an increase in buildings. Such an increase led to the expansion of a built-up area. Therefore, these studies substantiate that urban and peri-urban areas pose significant threats due to human activities. It becomes clear that there is a need for sustainable urban planning in urban and peri-urban areas to prevent or reduce the threats that human activities may pose.

Land use planning and management assesses land resources and determines the best ways to balance economic, social, and environmental needs.⁴ It aims to ensure sustainable development through efficient land resource allocation and ecological conservation.⁵ It deals with deciding how land should be used and the appropriate land division to accommodate different activities. This involves zoning regulations, rural and urban planning, and environmental considerations. Besides, land use planning and management focuses on enforcing land use plans to ensure sustainability and efficiency. Therefore, land use planning and management matters a lot because they prevent uncontrolled urban and peri-urban growth. In doing so, it enhances economic development while protecting the environment simultaneously. As a result, it becomes a primary tool for the struggle towards a sustainable future of urban and peri-urban areas.

¹ S. Seifollahi-Aghmiuni, et al, 'Urbanisation-Driven Land Degradation and Socioeconomic Challenges in Peri-Urban Areas: Insights from Southern Europe' (2022) 51 *Ambio* 1446 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-022-01701-7> accessed 19 February 2025.

² E.T. Mnyali and S.F. Materu, 'Analysis of the Current and Future Land Use/Land Cover Changes in Peri-Urban Areas of Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques' (2021) 47 *Tanzania Journal of Science* 1622.

³ N.A Munuo and J.M. Matindana, 'Modelling Expansion and Densification in Peri-Urban Areas: The Case of Goba Ward, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania' (*Journal of the Geographical Association of Tanzania*, Vol 41, No 2, 2022) 129.

⁴ G. Metternicht, *Land Use and Spatial Planning: Enabling Sustainable Management of Land Resources* (Springer 2018).

⁵ M. Song, Min An, et al., 'Research on Land Use Optimization Based on PSO-GA Model with the Goals of Increasing Economic Benefits and Ecosystem Services Value' (2025) 119 *Sustainable Cities and Society* 106072.

Given that urban and peri-urban areas are the main threats to human activities, their sustainable future rests upon land use planning and management as primary tools.

Effective policies and strategic decisions are necessary for sustainable urbanisation. Land use planning and management helps evidence-based policy formulation and decision-making. Moreover, urban and peri-urban areas pose environmental challenges; to mitigate them, land use planning and management controls the magnitude and patterns of these areas. The balance between economic growth and environmental protection around urban and peri-urban areas is achievable through land use planning and management. Land use planning and management also prevents overcrowding of urban and peri-urban areas, eventually improving living conditions through enhancing adequate infrastructure, housing, and public services. Furthermore, it is possible to integrate climate adaptation and mitigation strategies through land use planning, flood risk management, water resource management, and sustainable economic activities around urban and peri-urban areas.

Considering the above circumstances, this article critically evaluates how land planning laws in Tanzania can be a tool to limit population density, noise, and pollution, maintain the neighbourhood's aesthetics, and achieve the goal of a sustainable future. The focus of this article is Tanzania because of several reasons. First, Tanzania is home to diverse ecosystems.⁶ Hence, the increase of human activities in urban and peri-urban areas poses threats to the diverse ecosystems in the country. Second, because of rapid population growth, Tanzania is experiencing rapid urbanisation, especially in urban and peri-urban areas.⁷ As a result, environmental and socioeconomic challenges are posed by increased human activities in these regions. Therefore, drawing examples from Tanzania in this article provides a rich context for assessing land use planning and management and offers valuable insights that can be applied both locally and globally in the struggle to achieve a sustainable future in urban and peri-urban areas.

This article starts by providing an overview of land use planning laws in Tanzania. The rationale is to glance at all relevant laws that may apply to land use planning and management. This article will evaluate how land use planning laws limit population density, noise, and pollution, maintain the aesthetics of the neighbourhood, and achieve the goal of a sustainable future. Essentially, this part establishes how strong the land use planning laws are in the struggle for a sustainable future. Then, the article will argue whether the land use planning laws are sufficient to achieve the goal of a sustainable future. The essence of the part is to establish gaps, limitations and challenges emanating from the land use planning laws. Finally, this article shall make conclusive remarks on the way forward regarding land use planning laws to ensure they become effective enough to achieve a sustainable future.

⁶ F.P. Mbise, 'Determinants of Community Awareness Regarding the Endangered Rungwecebus kipunji in Tanzania' (2025) *Human Ecology* 1

⁷ G.J. Miringay, et al., 'Urban Territorial Regionalisation and the Emergence of Un-Ecological Rural Urbanism in City Localities: Case of Dodoma National Capital City, Tanzania' (2025).

2. OVERVIEW OF LAND PLANNING LAWS IN TANZANIA

Land use planning laws are indispensable to achieving a sustainable future in urban and peri-urban areas. These laws help to mitigate the significant threats that human activities pose in urban and peri-urban areas. Responsively, Tanzania has passed different laws to regulate land use and division of land based on various activities while considering environmental needs. Tanzania's Land use planning laws appear in three groups: the Constitution, primary, and secondary legislation.

The Constitution of Tanzania⁸ is the mother law of the land. It is often called mother law because, first, it is the supreme law of the land. This means that there is no other law above the Constitution. Also, all other laws derive their validity from the Constitution. This means that when other laws become inconsistent with the Constitution, they become void to the extent of their inconsistencies.⁹ The Constitution inspires the struggle to achieve a sustainable future by accommodating fundamental principles relevant to sustainability. It requires an integrated and balanced approach to planning and promoting the national economy.¹⁰ It also urges the harnessing and preservation of national wealth and heritage.¹¹ It directs the focus of national wealth to the development of the people.¹²

The primary legislation consists of the laws passed by the Parliament of the United Republic of Tanzania. The Parliament has the authority to pass laws from Articles 4 and 64 of the Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania. The primary legislation for land use planning and management are the Urban Planning Act¹³, the Land Use Planning Act¹⁴, and the Environmental Management Act.¹⁵ The Urban Planning Act was made for several purposes. First, to provide for orderly and sustainable land development in urban areas. Second, to preserve and improve amenities. Third, to provide for the grant of consent to develop land and powers of control over land use. Lastly, to provide for other related matters.

The primary purpose of the Land Use Planning Act is to provide for procedures for the preparation, administration, and enforcement of land use plans. The essence of the Environmental Management Act is to provide a legal and institutional framework for sustainable management of the environment. In addition, it outlines principles for management, impact and risk assessments, prevention and control of pollution, waste management, environmental quality standards, public participation, compliance, and enforcement. Moreover, it provides the basis for the implementation of international instruments on the environment. The purposes for enacting these laws indicate a struggle

⁸ The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania of 1977 as amended from time to time.

⁹ *Ibid*, Art 64(5).

¹⁰ *Ibid*, Art 9(d).

¹¹ *Ibid*, Art 9(c).

¹² *Ibid*, Art 9(i).

¹³ Act No. 8 of 2007.

¹⁴ Act No. 6 of 2007.

¹⁵ Act No. 20 of 2004.

to achieve a sustainable future in Tanzania. Besides, the Local Government (Urban Authorities) Act¹⁶ establishes urban authorities for local government to provide for those authorities' functions and related matters.

Subsidiary legislation is another category of laws relevant to land use planning and management. These are legislation made by bodies other than the Parliament. They are made under the constitutional delegation of legislative powers.¹⁷ One is the Local Government (Urban Authorities) (Development Control) Regulations¹⁸. Another is the Urban Planning (Use Groups and Use Classes) Regulations¹⁹, which categorises all uses of land and buildings.²⁰ Moreover, the Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations²¹ provide adequate and functional space standards.²² Furthermore, the Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations²³ prescribe zones for land use and colours.²⁴

After providing an overview of land planning laws in Tanzania, the section that follows will focus on how land planning laws can be tools for limiting population density, noise, and pollution, maintaining the aesthetics of the neighbourhood, and achieving the goal of a sustainable future. This is crucial because it aims to assess how land planning laws are employed to achieve this goal.

3. HOW LAND PLANNING LAWS LIMIT POPULATION DENSITY

The term population density means the intensity of use of land reckoned or expressed in terms of the number of persons, dwelling units' habitable rooms or any combination of those factors per unit area of land; and for this definition, habitable does not include a kitchen, store room, bathroom, or garage.²⁵ This means that the population is measured per unit of land area. Urban and peri-urban areas are prone to population density when their growth is not well controlled through land planning laws. Land planning laws of Tanzania limit population density through zoning classification, space standards prescription, and green space regulations.

Section 28(c) of the Urban Planning Act²⁶ powers the planning authority to formulate by-laws to regulate zoning regarding use and density of development. Under section 77(1)(e) of the Urban Planning Act²⁷, the minister responsible for land has the power to regulate the classification of industries into various classes for zoning purposes.

¹⁶ Cap 288 RE 2019.

¹⁷ The Constitution, Art 97(5).

¹⁸ GN No. 242 of 2008.

¹⁹ GN No. 91 of 2018.

²⁰ The Urban Planning (Use Groups and Use Classes) Regulations, Reg 3.

²¹ GN No. 93 of 2018.

²² The Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations, Reg 4(1).

²³ GN No. 92 of 2018.

²⁴ The Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations, Reg 3.

²⁵ The Urban Planning Act, s 2.

²⁶ Act No. 8 of 2007.

²⁷ Act No. 8 of 2007.

Moreover, according to section 7(e) of the Urban Planning Act, the planning authorities have the power to control the density of buildings on the land. The second Schedule to the Urban Planning Act prescribes the planning scheme to consider population growth, migration, density and distribution, age and sex structure, household sizes and household formation rates. In doing so, density may be limited to support sustainable urban growth. The Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations²⁸ were made to prescribe zones for land uses and colours.²⁹ Paragraph 1 of the First Schedule to the Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations prescribes several zones such as residential, commercial (Retail and Wholesale), industrial (Light, Medium, Heavy & Service), institutional, public utilities, beach, open spaces and recreational, transportation, communication and microwave towers, agricultural, water bodies, conservation, and economic development. Different zones imply different densities. Zoning regulations control population density.

Besides, the Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations³⁰ allocate the standards for residential areas, unplanned settlements, building height, building lines and setbacks, floor area, plot coverage and plot ratio, health facilities, education facilities, recreation facilities, beach facilities, golf course, passive and active recreation, public facilities by planning levels, public facilities by population size, parking and road width and agricultural show grounds.³¹ These standards dictate the size and layout of residential plots, minimum lot sizes, and building height limitations. In doing so, the standards directly impact the potential population density.

Limiting population density in a unit of land area is essential to prevent overcrowding. Overcrowding can cause competition for resources and amenities, which can transmit diseases easily and cause environmental degradation. Eventually, the quality of life of people residing in such land areas may be negatively impacted. Therefore, land planning laws mitigate urban sprawl in urban and peri-urban areas through zoning restrictions and space standards.

4. HOW LAND PLANNING LAWS LIMIT NOISE

In this article, noise implies a sound, especially loud or unpleasant, that causes disturbance. Statutorily, noise means any unwanted and annoying sound that is intrinsically objectionable to human beings or can have or is likely to hurt human health or the environment.³² The concentration of human activities in these areas causes noise. Heavy traffic, construction work, industrial operations, and social gatherings are the main activities in urban and peri-urban areas. Moreover, these activities occur in proximity. As a result, they lead to a cumulative sound pollution effect.

²⁸ G.N. No. 92 of 2018.

²⁹ The Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations, Reg 3.

³⁰ G.N. No. 93 of 2018.

³¹ the Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations, Reg 3.

³² Reg 3 of the Environmental Management (Standards for the Control of Noise and Vibrations Pollution) Regulations.

Land planning laws limit noise by defining specific land use and development zones. The Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations³³ empower the planning authority to assign a type of land use within a planning area. Land uses permitted by planning authorities in local planning areas include residential, commercial, industrial, institutional, public utilities, beaches, recreation, transportation, communication, agriculture, water bodies, conservation, and economic development.³⁴ The designation of different land use zones allows residential areas to be located away from industrial regions where excessive noise levels are predicted.

Moreover, land use control by the planning authority as per section 46 of the Land Use Planning Act³⁵ can limit noise in urban and peri-urban areas. This is done through implementing minimum distances between noise sources and residential places. The allocation of adequate and functional space per the Urban Planning Space Standards as per Regulation 4 of the Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations can limit noise in urban and peri-urban areas.

Besides, the Environmental Management (Standards for the Control of Noise and Vibrations Pollution) Regulations³⁶ prohibit a person from making or causing to be made any loud, unreasonable, unnecessary, or unusual noise that annoys, disturbs, injures, or endangers the comfort, repose, health, or safety of others and that of the environment.³⁷ Also, owners of machinery or facilities must ensure noise or vibration levels do not exceed permissible limits.³⁸ Sound level meters should be installed at the premises to monitor noise levels.³⁹ Violation of this regulation results in an offence.⁴⁰

5. HOW LAND PLANNING LAWS LIMIT POLLUTION

Due to the concentration of human activities in urban and peri-urban areas, these areas become prone to pollution.⁴¹ Heavy traffic, waste generation, industrial operations and limited space contribute significantly to air, water, and land pollution in urban and peri-urban areas. The term pollution here means the presence in or introduction into the environment of a substance with harmful or poisonous effects. Land planning laws intentionally design land use to reduce pollution, maintain water quality, regulate industrial zones, and promote sustainable practices, resulting in a lower environmental

³³ G. N. No. 92 of 2018.

³⁴ Paragraph 1 of the Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations.

³⁵ Act No. 6 of 2007.

³⁶ G.N. No. 32 of 2014.

³⁷ The Environmental Management (Standards for the Control of Noise and Vibrations Pollution) Regulations, Reg 7(1).

³⁸ Ibid, Reg 11(1).

³⁹ The Environmental Management (Standards for the Control of Noise and Vibrations Pollution) Regulations, Reg 11(2).

⁴⁰ Ibid, Reg 11(3).

⁴¹ J.J., Roberts, et al., 'A Critical Review of the Effect of Air Pollution Control Regulations on Land Use Planning' (1975) 25(5) *Journal of the Air Pollution Control Association* 500.

effect. In the case of *Iddi Babu v Grace Sillo Wawa & Others*⁴², the appellant testified that the noise from the generator caused disturbance to him and his family, causing a lack of sleep. He couldn't do his work correctly because of the disturbance. However, the nuisance the appellant claims falls under noise pollution, which is governed by the Environmental Management Act, No. 20 of 2004. Under this law, noise emission is regarded as noise pollution if it exceeds the minimum standards set by the National Environmental Standards Committee established under the Act.

Land planning laws limit pollution through land use plans. Section 4(a) of the Land Use Planning Act⁴³ establishes the essence of land use plans. It states that a land use plan aims to facilitate efficient and orderly land use management. In doing so, pollution can be limited. Land use plans manage how land can be used through the procedures and processes by which land use in a planning area or zone is prescribed, managed, monitored, and evaluated.⁴⁴ Land use plans can separate pollution-generating activities and industries from sensitive areas such as hospitals and residential areas. Hence, pollution can be limited through land use plans if there are strong enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance with regulations.

Moreover, one of the fundamental principles of urban planning, as established under section 3(f) of the Urban Planning Act, indicates the limitation of pollution. It states that all persons and authorities exercising powers, applying, or interpreting the urban plans shall be responsible for protecting the environment of human settlements and ecosystems from pollution, degradation, and destruction to attain sustainable development. This can be achieved through zoning restrictions and land use plans. Land use plans can protect natural lands, wetlands, and wildlife habitats from development activities that could disrupt ecosystems and contribute to pollution sources like construction runoff.

Besides, section 56 of the Land Use Planning Act⁴⁵ prescribes the monitoring and evaluation of land use plans. It prescribes issuing a land restoration order against someone causing harm to or likely to cause damage to land without requiring a complainant to prove a right or interest in the property or environment. Evidence comes from the case of *Festo Balegele and 794 others v Dar es Salaam City Council*.⁴⁶ Festo Balegele and 794 others filed an application against Dar es Salaam City Council for an order of certiorari to quash the decision to dump waste and refuse at Kunduchi Mtongani, a residential area in Dar es Salaam. The respondents argued that refuse collection and disposal were mandatory under the Local Government (Urban Authorities) Act. The applicants argued that the respondent had not considered relevant factors, such as the general land development plan, health hazards, and the area's location within the

⁴² (Civil Appeal 79 of 2016) [2018] TZHC 2724 (10 July 2018).

⁴³ Act No. 6 of 2007.

⁴⁴ The Land Use Planning Act, s 2.

⁴⁵ Act No. 6 of 2007.

⁴⁶ Misc. Civil Cause No. 90 of 1991.

designated garbage disposal sites. The court ruled that the refuse and waste disposal at Kunduchi Mtongani was ultra vires and prohibited further disposal.

Prohibiting noise pollution is also a mechanism through which land planning laws can limit pollution in urban and peri-urban areas. Section 106 of the Environmental Management Act provides for a general prohibition of pollution. Section 106(5) prohibits noise pollution. It states that no person shall emit or cause to emit noise over the standards prescribed or that may be specified by noise emission. In the case of *Iddi Babu v Grace Sillo Wawa & Others*⁴⁷, the appellant testified that the noise from the generator caused disturbance to him and his family, causing a lack of sleep. He couldn't do his work correctly because of the disturbance. However, the nuisance the appellant claims falls under noise pollution, which is governed by the Environmental Management Act, No. 20 of 2004. Under this law, noise emissions are regarded as noise pollution if they exceed the minimum standards set by the National Environmental Standards Committee established under the Act. The court observed that the appellant was supposed to submit his complaint to the National Environment Management Council (NEMC), which, through its Environmental Standards Committee, could have discovered whether or not the noise from the generator exceeded the minimum standard amounting to noise pollution.

6. HOW LAND PLANNING LAWS MAINTAIN AESTHETICS OF NEIGHBOURHOOD

When urban and peri-urban growth is not well regulated, aesthetics cannot be maintained in these areas. Aesthetics considers various land and environmental qualities in planning and development processes. The key attributes here include visual, cultural, and sensory ones. Henceforth, aesthetics is critical because it enables the creation and maintenance of functional land use and a visually pleasing and harmonious environment. To ensure urban and peri-urban areas grow while maintaining their aesthetics, land planning laws are important because they maintain aesthetics.

One of the ways the land planning laws maintain aesthetics is through the prescription of urban planning standards.⁴⁸ The Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations prescribe standards for urban planning.⁴⁹ The power to determine the space standards has been vested to the planning authority under the basis of section 38 of the Urban Planning Act.⁵⁰

⁴⁷ (Civil Appeal 79 of 2016) [2018] TZHC 2724 (10 July 2018).

⁴⁸ Reg 3 of the Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations define urban planning standards to mean the standards for residential areas, unplanned settlements, building height, building lines and setbacks, floor area, plot coverage and plot ratio, health facilities, education facilities, recreation facilities, beach facilities, golf course, passive and active recreation, public facilities by planning levels, public facilities by population size, parking and road width and agricultural show grounds.

⁴⁹ The Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations, Schedule.

⁵⁰ Act No. 8 of 2007.

This section requires each planning authority to determine planning space standards, the density of buildings on land, height, design, appearance and siting, and manner of access to land and buildings in its jurisdiction following a set of national standards. In doing so, aesthetics can be maintained in the urban and peri-urban areas. Moreover, the standards require developers to incorporate landscaping, green spaces, and parks into their projects. Another way is through the requirement of planning consent⁵¹ before land development. Section 29(1) of the Urban Planning Act obligates any person not to develop land without planning consent. Regulation 124 of the Local Government (Urban Authorities) (Development Control) Regulations requires anyone who intends to erect a building to seek and obtain a building permit, and Regulation 139 (1) prescribes the consequences of violating Regulation 124. It states that no person shall develop any land within a planning area without planning consent granted by the planning authority. The planning consent maintains aesthetics through dictating acceptable building materials, architectural styles, and landscaping.

Building permits must be under the laws. In the case of *Charles Kahatano Lwempisi v Bukoba Municipal Council*⁵², the court observed that it is trite law that a building permit issued by the Township Authority or Town Council or Municipal Council or City Council must comply with Regulation 124 stated herein above. In the matter, the purported building permit violated Regulation 124, while the drawings violated Regulation 135 (1), as already stated above. The court went further to observe that in the circumstances of this case, subjecting the purported building permit under the interpretation of Regulation 124 and subjecting the drawings under the interpretation of Regulation 135 (1), it is apparent that the same does not qualify to be termed as a ‘valid building permit’, likewise, the drawings do not qualify to be termed as ‘Approved drawings’ hence, both a nullity.

7. HOW LAND PLANNING LAWS ACHIEVE THE GOAL OF SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

One of the fundamental aims of urban planning is to ensure sustainable and orderly growth of urban and peri-urban areas by promoting and enforcing sustainable land use practices.⁵³ All persons and authorities are directed to improve the provision of infrastructure and social services for sustainable human settlement development.⁵⁴ Moreover, a sustainable future can be achieved through environmental protection. This means that in urban growth, persons and authorities must protect the environment of

⁵¹ Under section 2 of the Urban Planning Act, the term planning consent is defined to mean a consent to develop land within a planning area given by the authority empowered to give such consent pursuant the provisions of the Act.

⁵² (HC Land Case 3 of 2016) 2022 TZHC 9799 (6 May 2022).

⁵³ The Urban Planning Act, s 4(1)(c).

⁵⁴ *Ibid*, s 3(b).

human settlements and ecosystems from pollution, degradation and destruction to attain sustainable development.⁵⁵

The land planning laws enable the achievement of a sustainable future through the requirement of environmental impact assessment⁵⁶ before executing land development projects. Section 29(3) of the Urban Planning Act⁵⁷ imposes an obligation that the applicant must submit an environmental impact assessment report alongside the application for planning consent. This happens if a planning authority deems a development activity's environmental impact harmful. This provision assists the goal of achieving a sustainable future through environmental accountability in the land development process. How so? It requires developers to assess and address potential harm before projects like industrial sites, dumping areas, sewerage treatment plants, or quarries can proceed. Hence, it prevents irreversible damage to the ecosystems where the land development projects are executed.

The project was undertaken without an approved EIA report in the case of *Gaudensi George Milanzi & 19 Others v Masasi District Council & 2 Others*⁵⁸. The court faulted the authority for not complying with the requirement of the law of EIA. The court reasoned on page 11 that it could not be overemphasised that succumbing to social, economic, and political pressure to establish a training centre in the remotest of vicinities in our country in contravention of the tenets of sustainable development is unfit a tag to the third defendant. Finally, the court urged that within a reasonable time from this judgement, officially remind the first and third defendants of their duties to ensure observance of the rule of law and take into cognisance the environmental and social impacts of their current and future development projects. This may include conducting sensitisation seminars on the new and emerging concept of environmental rule of law in the context of sustainable development goals with specific emphasis on ecological procedural rights for all district executive directors in the country.

Besides, the designation of conservation areas promotes achieving a sustainable future. Section 50 of the Urban Planning Act⁵⁹ empowers the planning authority to designate conservation areas. Areas that can be subject to designation include exceptional architectural, historic, traditional, aesthetic, or biodiversity interests, such as the character or appearance of which is desirable to preserve or restore. In exercising this power, the planning authority must seek consultation with the Director of Antiquities, the Director of Environment and other relevant organs. In the designated conservation areas, no person shall, without the planning authority's consent, carry out any works within a conservation area.⁶⁰

⁵⁵ Ibid, s 3(f).

⁵⁶ Section 3 of the Environmental Management Act defines the term environmental impact assessment. It states that environmental impact assessment" means a systematic examination conducted to determine whether or not a programme, activity or project will have any adverse impacts on the environment.

⁵⁷ Act No. 8 of 2007.

⁵⁸ (Land Case No.1 of 2021) [2023] TZHC 21541 (29 September 2023).

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ The Urban Planning Act, s 51(1).

8. WHETHER LAND PLANNING LAWS ARE EFFICIENT

After evaluation of mechanisms that land planning laws employ to limit population density, noise, and pollution, maintain the aesthetics of the neighbourhood, and achieve the goal of a sustainable future, it is high time at this juncture to assess whether these laws are sufficient in the struggle for a sustainable future, especially in urban and peri-urban areas. The land planning laws that form the subject of assessment in this part include the Urban Planning Act, the Land Use Planning Act, the Environmental Management Act, Local Government (Urban Authorities) (Development Control) Regulations, the Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations, the Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations, and the Urban Planning (Use Groups and Use Classes) Regulations.

As a general rule, the above-mentioned land planning laws significantly contribute to orderly and sustainable development, balancing economic growth and environmental protection in urban and peri-urban areas. Their contribution is through different mechanisms such as planning consent⁶¹ and building permit⁶², zoning restrictions⁶³, environmental impact assessment⁶⁴, urban planning space standards⁶⁵, designation of conservation areas⁶⁶, land suitability assessment⁶⁷, historic or architectural interests⁶⁸, and land use plans and their monitoring and enforcement⁶⁹ to mention but a few. Zoning restricts the type and intensity of development in certain areas, hence limiting population density. For example, the Morogoro Master Plan (2015-2035) aims to formalise informal areas while adding green corridors. The 2016-2036 Dar es Salaam Master Plan tries to formalise these areas, pushing for mid-rise buildings to house more people vertically rather than sprawling outward.⁷⁰

Designating conservation areas and historic or architectural interests can maintain neighbourhoods' visual character and aesthetics. For instance, in Stone Town, Zanzibar, strict zoning preserves its UNESCO-listed Swahili architecture. New buildings must match historic heights and styles, keeping the coral-stone charm intact. It's a success story of planning and maintaining identity.

However, the effectiveness of the land planning laws is limited. One of the limitations is the discretionary power the planning authorities have to permit a change of use of planned areas under exceptional circumstances for public interests.⁷¹ This opens a room for subjective interpretation, which can lead to potential abuse. As a result, it

⁶¹ The Urban Planning Act, s 29(1).

⁶² The Local Government (Urban Authorities) (Development Control) Regulations, Regs 124 and 139.

⁶³ The Urban Planning (Zoning of Land Uses) Regulations, Reg 3 and First Schedule.

⁶⁴ The Urban Planning Act, s 29(3) and section 81 of the Environmental Management Act.

⁶⁵ The Urban Planning (Planning and Space Standards) Regulations, Reg 4 and Schedule.

⁶⁶ The Urban Planning Act, ss 50 and 51.

⁶⁷ The Land Use Planning Act, s 27.

⁶⁸ The Urban Planning Act, s 58.

⁶⁹ The Land Use Planning Act, s 57.

⁷⁰ Dar es Salaam City Council, Dar es Salaam Master Plan 2016-2036 (2016) 20-25.

⁷¹ The Urban Planning (Use Groups and Use Classes) Regulations, Reg 4(1).

hinders the goal of a sustainable future in urban and peri-urban areas. Moreover, no criteria have been stipulated in the laws that guide the planning authorities during the renewal of planning consent for the period it may consider necessary.⁷² This leads to potential abuse of such power.

The land planning laws allow subjective decision-making. For instance, section 29(3) of the Urban Planning Act⁷³ imposes subjective decision-making about undertaking environmental impact assessment. The planning authority's judgement is heavily relied upon to assess the possible negative environmental impact as per the mentioned provision of the law. Different authorities may perceive the same proposal differently due to this subjectivity, which could lead to inconsistent decision-making and possibly unfair treatment of applicants. Additionally, not all activities that potentially significantly influence the environment are covered by the provision, leaving gaps in environmental protection for other kinds of developments that are not explicitly specified.

Besides, non-compliance with land use planning and management in urban and peri-urban areas has limited the sufficiency of laws in achieving a sustainable future.⁷⁴ A study by Mashalla on the effectiveness of urban land development control in Tanzania reveals that high urban population growth has led to uncontrolled developments, highlighting ineffective land development control due to weak enforcement of the land planning laws in Mbeya City.⁷⁵ Hence, regulatory bodies cannot often enforce land planning laws effectively.⁷⁶

9. CONCLUSION

The land planning laws of Tanzania give a good framework for managing population density, noise, pollution, and aesthetics. Still, their effectiveness is hampered by implementation issues. Therefore, it is necessary to address these concerns. This necessitates increased enforcement, improved urban planning initiatives, and a commitment to sustainable development. Tanzanian cities would continue to suffer the detrimental effects of uncontrolled growth, weakening attempts to build a sustainable future. The author recommends legislative amendments to remove the discretionary powers that authorities can potentially abuse. This is because the effectiveness of laws is based upon their execution. Tanzania needs more than statutes; it needs inspectors, funds, and local muscle to turn plans into reality.

⁷² The Urban Planning Act, s 33.

⁷³ Act No. 8 of 2007.

⁷⁴ United Nations Environment Programme, Msimbazi River Basin: Pollution Assessment Report (UNEP 2022) 15.

⁷⁵ J.B., Mashalla, *Effectiveness of Urban Land Development Control in Tanzania: The Case of Mbeya City* (Ardhi University, 2017).

⁷⁶ Ardhi University, 'Air Quality Monitoring in Dar es Salaam: Mikocheni Industrial Area' (2023) Environmental Studies Working Paper 12/2023, 8 (PM_{2.5} levels at 35 µg/m³), as aggregated by IQAir, 'Dar es Salaam Air Quality Index' (2023) <https://www.iqair.com> accessed 26 February 2025.